

Family Resemblances: “game” network analysis

Ludwig Wittgenstein's theory of "family resemblances," as elaborated in "Philosophical Investigations" (see also Ryan and Thon), offers a complex approach to conceptual understanding. Wittgenstein articulates the fluidity and overlapping semantic traits within categorical groups. His perspective challenges the classical idea of fixed essences, advocating for a recognition of overlapping traits that are like a family whose members share a constellation of features, behaviors, and characteristics without possessing a single defining attribute. So do semantic features of a general concept exhibit a series of similarities without a universal commonality. As such, the theory embraces the rich, interwoven network of similarities that characterize the myriad ways in which we use concepts. Through use, we access a specific subset of semantic traits that are recognized for a particular context.

*Don't say: There must be something common, or they would not be called 'games' "—but look and see whether there is anything common to all.—
For if you look at them you will not see something that is common to all, but similarities, relationships, and a whole series of them at that.*

Wittgenstein exemplifies his theory by looking at "game" and shows that when we investigate the different uses of the word game, we discover that while many correspondences can be found between uses, there are many features that drop out and others that appear. When looking at *board-games, card-games, chess, noughts and crosses, ball-games, a child's game of throwing a ball*, we should investigate *similarities and relations* in terms of *competition, amusement, winning and losing*, different types of *skill*, such as *skill in chess* and *skill in tennis, luck* etc. The similarities, correspondences and relationships between the features that appear or, in other cases, drop out form *a complicated network of similarities overlapping and criss-crossing: sometimes overall similarities, sometimes similarities of detail.*

In *From Fictional Worlds to Virtual Worlds. Drivers of Change Between Perspectives on Fictional, Virtual, and Real* we illustrated his analysis of *game* by mapping the relationship between the different uses and corresponding semantic traits into a dynamic Kumu chart:

Figure 1. The map for Family Resemblance Network: *game*.
 The Dynamic model is available at <https://embed.kumu.io/915cf7643f105963360297b55f74a924>.

The following series of images illustrates the various degrees of relationships within the family. We start by isolating all the uses that share the feature *business* (as an example) in Figure 2. The results are *game the system*, *the stock game*, and *this is not a game (it's serious)*. However, these three uses also present other semantic features, illustrated in the next figure. We observe that the new features are *skill*, *seriousness*, *score*, *activity*, *winning/losing*, *dishonesty*, *risk*, and *luck*. In turn, each feature is shared by other uses, so on the next level, new uses can be observed (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Family Resemblance Network: *game*. Focused on *business*.

Figure 3. Family Resemblance Network: *game*. Focused on *business* level 2.

Figure 4. Family Resemblance Network: *game*. Focused on *business* level 3.

The next level of the relationship is, in this case, the entire network, when all the nodes are revealed.

Expanding on this complex web of relationships, there is a crucial aspect encapsulated by the term *family*. Wittgenstein draws on the notion of a family to underscore his rejection of the notion that all members of a category share a common core of similarities. In a family, for any given feature, there is at least one other member that shares it, but no trait is shared by all.